

An initial map of European intertidal seagrass

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ARTICLE INFO

Editor: Dr. Menghua Wang

Keywords:

Intertidal seagrass
European scale
Mapping
Coastal
Neural network

ABSTRACT

Seagrass meadows directly and indirectly provide a wide range of ecosystem services, but their close proximity to anthropogenic activities renders them highly vulnerable. Regardless of their vulnerability and importance as ecosystem health indicators, intertidal seagrasses, unlike their subtidal relatives, have yet to be assessed at continental scales, and current global estimates of seagrass extent either do not mention intertidal seagrasses or combine them with subtidal seagrasses. Here, we present a first of its kind map of intertidal seagrasses in Europe using a harmonised methodology. Over a total intertidal area of 15,100 km², we found that seagrasses cover an area comparable to the combined areas of Paris and Lisbon: 212 ± 18.8 km². The proportion of available intertidal area covered by seagrass decreased towards higher latitudes (from ~5.4 % at 35°N to ~0 % at 58°N). Regardless of this pattern, the top three hotspots of seagrass covered the full latitudinal range of Europe, notably in the North Frisian Wadden Sea (Germany), Arcachon Bay (France) and Ria Formosa (Portugal). Furthermore, we showed latitudinal gradients in seagrass cover, with higher cover in low latitudes and lower cover in high latitudes. Finally, an almost linear change in intertidal seagrass peak timing (day of the year of maximum seagrass cover) with latitude was found, with peak timing later the further south. This is a 'Call-to-Action' for data that are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). We present critical data for prioritising and developing policies, management and protection mechanisms across local, regional or international scales to safeguard these important ecosystems and the societies that depend upon them.

1. Introduction

Globally, coastal marine areas form some of the densest biodiversity hotspots, such as seagrasses, mangroves and saltmarshes, which can cover vast portions of the intertidal area. These habitats support ecosystems with significant ecological and socioeconomic value. Seagrasses specifically provide key habitats for both fisheries and non-fisheries

species (Unsworth et al., 2019b; Whitfield, 2017; Zoffoli et al., 2023); bolster tourism and recreation (do Amaral Camara Lima et al., 2023); regulate climate by sequestering carbon (Duarte and Krause-Jensen, 2017; Sousa et al., 2019); stabilise sediments along coastlines, minimising erosion (Paul and Amos, 2011) and aid in water quality improvements (Orth et al., 2020). These coastal habitats, and especially intertidal habitats exposed to both aquatic and atmospheric conditions,

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2025.115116>

Received 16 January 2025; Received in revised form 29 October 2025; Accepted 30 October 2025

Available online 4 November 2025

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are highly vulnerable to human impacts (Cardoso et al., 2004; Gardmendia et al., 2021; Momota and Hosokawa, 2021) and are widely regarded as indicators of ecosystem health (Foden and Brazier, 2007; Krause-Jensen et al., 2005).

Within the European context, the conservation, management and restoration of seagrasses are ranked as high priorities. Their importance and elevated vulnerability guided their inclusion within the European Union (EU) Habitats Directive, Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC), Marine Strategy Framework Directive, Biodiversity Strategies to 2020/2030 and Nature Restoration Law 2024. Specifically, within the Water Framework Directive, seagrasses are defined as *biological quality elements*, and have been named Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) and Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) (Foden and Brazier, 2007; Krause-Jensen et al., 2005; Miloslavich et al., 2018; Pereira et al., 2013). Likewise, seagrass restoration is one of the main targets of the Nature Restoration Law (EU, 2024). This emphasis is mirrored globally within strategies such as the Barcelona Convention (1995), the United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN). However, the main obstacle for conservation is the lack of available data at national, regional and international scales (Unsworth et al., 2019a).

The critical initial step in monitoring, managing and ultimately protecting these important ecosystems is to know their location, extent and condition. Yet, consistent spatial data on intertidal seagrass are lacking, not only globally but also at national and regional scales. While there are some examples of broader national and regional scale intertidal seagrass mapping (Beca-Carretero et al., 2024; Clemente et al., 2023; Davies et al., 2024a, 2024b; Dolch et al., 2017; van Katwijk et al., 2024), a range of different methods from satellite observation, field survey and species distribution modelling were used to create such data. These data are then often aggregated irrespective of the employed methodologies (Dunic et al., 2021; de Los Santos et al., 2019; Turschwell et al., 2021). This inconsistency of data creation raises issues of temporal and spatial mismatches (de Los Santos et al., 2019), spatial bias for areas of previously known intertidal seagrass extent (Clemente et al., 2023; Davies et al., 2024a, 2024b), inappropriate combination of subtidal and intertidal seagrasses (Dunic et al., 2021; Turschwell et al., 2021) or highlighting potential niche locations for seagrass as a habitat, regardless of true presence (Beca-Carretero et al., 2024).

The majority of intertidal seagrass mapping has relied upon more traditional time-consuming field data collection, which struggles to cover whole meadow areas without extensive time and effort investment. In recent years, mapping at meadow scales (more than 1 km²) has become increasingly possible through remote sensing (Lizcano-Sandoval et al., 2022; Zoffoli et al., 2023; Zoffoli et al., 2020, 2021). The most common mapping methods utilise vegetation indices from satellite imagery and rely upon the assumption of intertidal vegetation being dominated by monospecific seagrass beds, potentially overlooking mixed vegetation communities. Recent advances in remote-sensing techniques, cloud-computing and machine learning have markedly improved classification capabilities in heterogeneous intertidal areas (Zhang et al., 2024). However, machine learning applications for mapping intertidal seagrasses have remained limited to specific individual seagrass meadows (Davies et al., 2024a, 2024b) and currently are unable to distinguish the different species of seagrass found within the intertidal area. It is imperative that the distribution and extent of intertidal seagrass be available to aid policy and management of these important and vulnerable habitats, which form a vital link between terrestrial and marine ecosystems.

Here we utilised the neural network model Intertidal Classification of Europe: Categorising Reflectance of Emerged Areas of Marine vegetation with Sentinel-2 (ICE CREAMS) (Davies et al., 2024a, 2024b) alongside a cloud-computing mosaic approach to create a high-resolution (10 m per pixel) European-wide map of the maximum intertidal seagrass coverage (between 2018 and 2023). ICE CREAMS is a deep learning neural network model specifically developed for Sentinel-2, trained with

373,814 pixels of intertidal vegetation, which provided intertidal seagrass classification accuracy of 82 %. The aim of this work was to (1) improve the ICE CREAMS classification accuracy, (2) use this updated model to create an accurate contemporary map of intertidal seagrass across Europe; (3) provide a robust and scalable methodology for continental scale intertidal seagrass mapping; (4) provide an open access tool for stakeholders and policy-makers to allow the delivery of the best informed management decisions and (5) lead a ‘‘Call-to-Action’’ for the availability of data following Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) principles (Miloslavich et al., 2018; Nordlund et al., 2024; Ratnarajah et al., 2022).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. General overview

To provide a full map of intertidal seagrass across Europe, the first task is to create a remote sensing derived image to classify that covers the full intertidal area of Europe. To maintain the spectral signature of vegetation it is essential for that imagery to not be covered by water or clouds (i.e. intertidal zones are observed at a time of low-tide without cloud cover). One image taken of Europe at the same time will have areas where it is low-tide and areas where it is high-tide. Therefore, a composite image needs to be made that selects imagery that occurred at low-tide and without clouds (‘quality mosaic’ henceforth). Furthermore, we want our quality mosaic to display the moment when seagrass was at its peak density, to do this we select the moment when each location had the greatest Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI, a proxy of vegetation density). However, intertidal areas are highly dynamic and are subject to ephemeral macroalgae blooms, that may cover other vegetation for short periods of time. Likewise, dead seagrass or other vegetation may wash up on the shore where there is normally no vegetation. Therefore, to make sure we do not over- or under-estimate seagrass cover we created 5 of these maximised vegetation quality mosaics, and only considered an area to be seagrass if 3 out of the 5 mosaics were classified as seagrass.

We created these 5 vegetation quality mosaics maximising the NDVI for the European Intertidal area using ~20 trillion pixels from 6 years of Sentinel-2 imagery (2.14×10^{13} pixels from 2018 to 2023) over the 15,100 km² of intertidal area using a global intertidal mask (Murray et al., 2019), where intertidal is defined as areas that are completely covered by water at high tide (i.e. not including saltmarshes) and emerged at low-tide. Once these quality mosaics were made, we needed to classify them based on their spectral information to create vegetation maps of the intertidal. When combined with the Intertidal Classification of Europe: Categorising Reflectance of Emerged Areas of Marine vegetation using Sentinel-2 (ICE CREAMS v1.3) model (Updated from: Davies et al., 2024a, 2024b) this provided 5 classified maps of European intertidal vegetation. ICE CREAMS is a deep learning neural network model specifically developed for Sentinel-2, originally trained with 373,814 pixels of intertidal vegetation, which provided intertidal seagrass classification accuracy of 82 % (Davies et al., 2024a, 2024b). Here, ICE CREAMS v1.3, with an increased total of 738,004 training pixels, was validated on 61,162 independently labelled pixels and then applied to the maximised NDVI mosaics. The intertidal seagrass cover map was created by taking the areas where seagrass was the dominant prediction (at least 3 instances out of the 5 mosaics) from the ICE CREAMS outputs from the quality mosaics and computing the seagrass cover from the NDVI (Davies et al., 2024a, 2024b; Zoffoli et al., 2020). The mode was used to minimise any potential over-prediction of seagrass by the model or ephemeral macroalgal growth events (e.g. rapid green algae growth or drifting brown algae covering seagrass beds) resulting in under prediction of seagrass. For every pixel classified as seagrass from the mode prediction, seagrass cover was calculated using the greatest NDVI value predicted as seagrass (Zoffoli et al., 2020). The effective area occupied

by intertidal seagrass was taken as the sum of seagrass cover ('cumulative intertidal seagrass area' henceforth), as each pixel has an area of 100 m². Due to the limited sensitivity of remote sensing at detecting low cover seagrasses and the inherent elevated uncertainty at low covers of seagrass, only seagrasses over 50 % cover were assessed. The timing (average ± 95 % CI for day of the year) and predicted uncertainty were also recorded to provide information on seagrass peak timing and model estimate uncertainty. An interactive version of the high-resolution (10m) spatially and temporally explicit European Intertidal Seagrass map with associated uncertainty are accessible, both as a web map and raw data (<https://s2maxextenticcreams.projects.earthengine.app/view/europeanintertidalseagrass> & 10.5281/zenodo.17495492). Due to the extreme mismatch in intertidal scales between Atlantic (~15,100 km²) and Mediterranean (~697 km²), only results pertaining to the Atlantic coastline are analysed and discussed here.

2.2. Model update and validation

2.2.1. ICE CREAMS v1.1

The ICE CREAMS model is a neural network tabular learner from the FastAI framework in Python v3 (Howard and Gugger, 2020; Van Rossum and Drake, 2009). ICE CREAMS v1.1 consisted of 373,814 labelled pixels consisting of 26 features (12 BOA reflectances, 12 standardised reflectances, NDVI and NDWI), with labels covering 9 classes: Bare Sand, Bare Mud, Ulvophyceae (green macroalgae), Magnoliopsida (seagrass), Microphytobenthos (unicellular photosynthetic eukaryotes and cyanobacteria), Mixed-Rocks and Phaeophyceae (brown macroalgae), Rhodophyta (red macroalgae), Xanthophyceae (yellow-green macroalgae) and Water (Davies et al., 2024a, 2024b).

2.2.2. ICE CREAMS v1.3

ICE CREAMS v1.3 was created by retraining the ICE CREAMS model on a training data set with an increased total number of labelled pixels (738,004), while maintaining all other training parameters and model architectures from v1.1 (2 hidden layers, 26,761 trainable parameters and fine-tuned across 20 epochs using the ADaptive Moment estimation (ADAM) optimiser). These new labelled pixels were derived from a combination of multispectral Uncrewed Aerial Vehicle (UAV) data and visual interpretation of pixel spectra to provide both geographically and temporally explicit delineation of known intertidal habitats (Oiry et al., 2025; Oiry et al., 2024). The increase in pixels came from four classes: 7716 Rhodophyta, 145,049 Bare Sediment, 193,102 Microphytobenthos and 21,011 Water.

2.2.3. Validation comparison

To ensure that the increase in training pixels from ICE CREAMS v1.1 to v1.3 improved model performance, a validation dataset, updated from the validation data from Davies et al. (2024b), was created from across Europe. The data ranged from 2018 to 2025, covering 7 classes (Bare Sediment, Chlorophyta, Magnoliopsida, Microphytobenthos, Phaeophyceae, Rhodophyta and Water) and from a range of sources, such as geo-referenced quadrats, ultra high resolution drone imagery and photo interpretation. These geographically and temporally explicit delineations of known intertidal habitats were then aligned with Level-2 A (L2A) Sentinel-2 A/B/C images that coincided spatially and temporally (+/- 15 days). Following this, all reflectance values were extracted to create a validation data set consisting of 61,162 labelled Sentinel-2 pixels (Currently on github but will be uploaded to Zenodo when manuscript is published https://github.com/BedeFfinian/ICE_CREAMS/blob/main/Data/Input/Validation/Validation_Europe_LabelledS2.csv). ICE CREAMS v1.1 and v1.3 were then applied to these data and the global accuracy (G_a Eq. 1) and F1 score ($F1$ Eq. 2) were calculated across all validation data as binary presence or absence of seagrass:

$$G_a = \frac{n_{TP} + n_{TN}}{n_{TP} + n_{TN} + n_{FP} + n_{FN}} \quad (1)$$

$$F1 = \frac{n_{TP}}{n_{TP} + 0.5*(n_{FP} + n_{FN})} \quad (2)$$

where n_{TP} is the number of True Positives, n_{TN} the number of True Negatives, n_{FP} the number of False Positives and n_{FN} the number of False Negatives.

2.3. Composite preprocessing

2.3.1. Intertidal masking

As the ICE CREAMS model was trained on intertidal classes, all areas outside the intertidal zone needed to be removed prior to classification. An intertidal mask at 30 m resolution from 2016 was used as a starting point to create the spatial intertidal mask, which aims to include tidal flats for the study area (Murray et al., 2019). The NDVI and the Normalised Difference Water Index (NDWI) (Gao, 1996) were calculated for all pixels of the 6-year archive of Sentinel-2 L2A imagery that occurred within 900 m of the previous intertidal mask. For every pixel, the difference between the 99th and 1st percentile was calculated for both NDVI and NDWI (Eq. 3 & Eq. 4), and all pixels where these differences were both above 0.7 as well as the 99th percentile of NDVI being above 0.02 were selected.

$$NDVI = \frac{R(832) - R(664)}{R(832) + R(664)} \quad (3)$$

$$NDWI = \frac{R(560) - R(832)}{R(560) + R(832)} \quad (4)$$

where $R(560)$, $R(664)$ and $R(832)$ correspond to the surface reflectance (R) for the Sentinel-2 spectral domains in the green (560 nm), red (664 nm) and near-infrared (832 nm), respectively.

This selected for areas that were both commonly flooded (negative NDVI and positive NDWI) and commonly dry (positive NDVI and negative NDWI), thus likely to be intertidal areas that experience both high and low tides.

2.3.2. Cloud masking

While the Scene Classification Layer (SCL band) from the Sentinel-2 L2A dataset is commonly used for image filtering, it is based on tile metadata instead of per-pixel statistics, increasing the probability to include noisy pixels within the analysis. To optimise this image filtering and cloud masking process, two published developed methods were combined. First, we reduced the cloud probability dataset ('COPERNICUS/S2_CLOUD_PROBABILITY') into per-pixel probabilities for each image, applying a 15 % mean cloud-cover threshold for each clipped tile according to the designed coastal geometry assets (Roca et al., 2022). Second, to mask the remaining clouds and cloud shadows, we used the Cloud Score + method (CS+: 'GOOGLE/CLOUD_SCORE_PLUS/V1/S2_HARMONIZED'), an integrated model in Google Earth Engine (GEE) (Gorelick et al., 2017) that uses a maximum likelihood estimate of terrain illumination (Pasquarella et al., 2023). The cloud masking was performed using the CS+ Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of Quality Assessment (QA) band 'cs_cdf' at a 0.6 threshold (Lee et al., 2025).

2.3.3. Inaccurate spectra masking

After both intertidal and cloud masking, a small minority of pixels remained where the spectral shape was either inaccurate or illogical. This manifested in pixels with flat spectra, all bands with very small or very high values, or pixels where one band on its own had very high or low values relative to all the other bands. To better address this issue, normalised ratios between multiple different band combinations were created and thresholds set. These included ratios between lower wavelength bands and the near-infrared (Eq. 5 & Eq. 6) and the red (Eq. 7 & Eq. 8):

$$\frac{R(832) - R(443)}{R(832) + R(443)} > 0.15 \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{R(832) - R(490)}{R(832) + R(490)} > 0.2 \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{R(443) - R(664)}{R(443) + R(664)} < 0.2 \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{R(560) - R(664)}{R(560) + R(664)} < 0.2 \quad (8)$$

where $R(443)$, $R(490)$, $R(560)$, $R(664)$ and $R(832)$ being the Sentinel-2 bands for aerosols (443 nm), blue (490 nm), green (560 nm), red (664 nm) and near-infrared (832 nm) spectral domains, respectively. These ratios removed totally flat spectra, or pixels that included abnormally high reflectance in the aerosol or blue portion of the spectra in relation to the red and near-infrared portions.

2.3.4. Solid structure masking

To avoid applying the ICE CREAMS model on habitats of the intertidal area that the model has not been trained to identify, such as Salt-marsh, Rocky Reef or vertical cliffs, a solid structure mask was created using time series of Sentinel-1 Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data from within GEE. Both co- and cross-polarisation (VV and VH) bands of the calibrated SAR data were summarised from within the previous intertidal mask for the year 2022. For each pixel and each band, the 90th percentile (VV_{90} and VH_{90}) and standard deviation (VV_{σ} and VH_{σ}) were calculated, and thresholds were set for pixels of high structural complexity (i.e. high VV_{90} and VH_{90} ; Eq. 9 & Eq. 10) and high variation due to emersion and immersion during tidal cycles (i.e. high VV_{σ} and VH_{σ} ; Eq. 11 & Eq. 12), as follows:

$$VV_{90} > -10 \quad (9)$$

$$VH_{90} > -17 \quad (10)$$

$$VV_{\sigma} > 1 \quad (11)$$

$$VH_{\sigma} > 1 \quad (12)$$

These pixels were defined as being solid and complex structures based on histogram inspection, and therefore masked from analysis.

2.4. Quality mosaic

For all pixels remaining after these masking steps (2.14×10^{13} pixels), a quality mosaic, containing all available bands of Sentinel-2, that maximised NDVI was created, generating the first composite. All Sentinel-2 bands with lower spatial resolution than 10 m were resampled to match the high resolution bands. The quality mosaic selects the pixel with the greatest NDVI, while maintaining the accompanying spectral values of the pixel. To create the second composite, the same steps were followed while the values associated with the first composite were not considered in quality mosaicing. This workflow was followed to create the top five quality mosaics, where the previous quality mosaics were never considered for the next mosaic level. These five quality mosaics each consisted of ~61 million pixels and 14 bands (the 12 bands of Sentinel-2, NDVI and NDWI) at 10 m resolution.

2.5. Model application

The ICE CREAMS v1.3 model was applied to all quality mosaics to provide a classification and model probability value for all intertidal pixels within Europe. All 5 classifications were stacked, and the mode classification (at least three of the same class) of each pixel retrieved. Seagrass cover, calculated from the NDVI (Davies et al., 2024a, 2024b;

Zoffoli et al., 2020), was then taken when the mode class was predicted as seagrass and the cover was above 50 % (NDVI > 0.42) for the instances of seagrass predicted.

2.6. Data extraction

Data for both the Atlantic and Mediterranean coastlines were extracted by summarising by either country or half-degree latitude slices, from 35°N to 58.5°N in the Atlantic and from 31.5°N to 42.5°N in the Mediterranean. For each area (for example: Atlantic Coastline from 35°N to 35.5°N), total intertidal area, cumulative intertidal seagrass area (sum of seagrass cover values), cumulative intertidal seagrass uncertainty (τ Eq. 13), cumulative intertidal seagrass area for different seagrass cover bins (50–60 %, 60–70 % etc.), ‘Peak’ (mean day of the year with the greatest NDVI and mode class across the 5 classifications was seagrass) and ‘Peak’ uncertainty (95 % CI: T Eq. 14) were calculated.

The total seagrass uncertainty for each area (τ) was calculated as the inverse of the median of the sum of the per pixel probabilities ($\overline{\Sigma p}$) from the 5 classifications multiplied by the the area (A) and the global accuracy (G_a) of the model when applied to validation data (Davies et al., 2024a, 2024b):

$$\tau = \frac{A \times G_a \times (5 - \overline{\Sigma p})}{5} \quad (13)$$

The ‘Peak’ uncertainty for each area (T) was calculated by dividing the standard deviation of the ‘Peak’ (s_{DOY}) by the square root of the number of values (N_{DOY}):

$$T = \frac{s_{DOY}}{\sqrt{N_{DOY}}} \quad (14)$$

Seagrass cover, model uncertainty and ‘Peak’ timing (day of the year) were then cumulatively summarised by 10 % bins across latitude and EEZs of all European countries.

2.7. Seagrass hotspots

To delineate seagrass hotspots, we aimed to highlight only areas with consistently high seagrass cover across large spatial extents. We achieved this by applying a spatial average with a moving window of 300 m radius to all seagrass cover using the *ee.Image.reduceNeighborhood* and *ee.Kernel.square* methods from GEE; we defined a hotspot as where this averaged value was at least 80 % and covered a continuous area of above 1 km². Previous assessments of seed dispersal in the *Zostera* genus has shown high variability from below a km to tens of kms (Orth et al., 2006). Therefore, all 1 km² areas that occurred within 10 km of each other were grouped as the same hotspot, then the full extent of each hotspot was calculated (‘total hotspot area’, henceforth).

2.8. Statistical analysis

General Additive Models (GAMs) (Wood, 2017) were used to assess the proportion of intertidal area covered by seagrass (1: Eq. 15), the proportion of different seagrass covers (2: Eq. 16) and the change in Seasonality of peak intertidal seagrass (3: Eq. 17), all in relation to latitude. Model parameters were estimated within a Bayesian framework using the ‘brms’ and ‘RStan’ packages in R to leverage the Stan language (Bürkner, 2021; Carpenter et al., 2017; R Core Team, 2023; Stan Development Team, 2018). The response variables were assumed to follow Student-t (1 and 3) and Beta (2) distributions with weakly informative priors. Model parameters were estimated using Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling, with 4 chains of 10,000 iterations and a warm-up of 500. GAMs are a robust modelling framework that allow the user to describe non-linear relationships (Umlauf et al., 2018), while performing them in a Bayesian framework allows the user to include the uncertainty within these models (Turner et al., 2015).

2.8.1. Change in seagrass with latitude (1)

Observed proportion, which has been centred and scaled ($E^*_i = \frac{E_i - \bar{E}}{\sigma_E}$), of intertidal area covered by seagrass (E^*_i) and its uncertainty (τ_i) were modelled as a function of latitude with a thin plate basis spline ($f(L_i)$).

$$\begin{aligned}
 E^*_i &\sim \text{Student}(E_i, \tau_i) \\
 E_i &\sim \text{Student}(\mu_i, \sigma_i) \\
 \mu_i &= a + f(L_i) \\
 a &\sim \text{Student}(3, 0, 2.5) \\
 f(L_i) &\sim \text{Student}(3, 0, 2.5) \\
 \sigma &\sim \text{Student}(3, 0, 2.5)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{15}$$

2.8.2. Change in seagrass cover with latitude (2)

Observed proportion of intertidal area covered by seagrass cover (E^*_i) and its uncertainty (τ_i) were modelled as a function of latitude with a thin plate basis spline ($f(L_i)$) across Cover bins (ρ).

$$\begin{aligned}
 E^*_i &\sim \text{Beta}(E_i, \tau_i) \\
 E_i &\sim \text{Beta}(\mu_i, \phi_i) \\
 \mu_i &= a + f(L_i) : \rho \\
 a &\sim \text{Student}(3, 0, 2.5) \\
 f(L_i) : \rho &\sim \text{Student}(3, 0, 2.5) \\
 \phi &\sim \text{gamma}(0.01, 0.01)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{16}$$

2.8.3. Change in seasonality of seagrass peak with latitude (3)

Observed Day of Year, which has been centred and scaled ($DOY^*_i = \frac{DOY_i - \overline{DOY}}{\overline{DOY}}$), of peak seagrass (DOY^*_i) and its uncertainty (T_i) were modelled as a function of latitude with a thin plate basis spline ($f(L_i)$).

$$\begin{aligned}
 DOY^*_i &\sim \text{Student}(DOY_i, T_i) \\
 DOY_i &\sim \text{Student}(\mu_i, \sigma_i) \\
 \mu_i &= a + f(L_i) \\
 a &\sim \text{Student}(3, 0, 2.5) \\
 f(L_i) &\sim \text{Student}(3, 0, 2.5) \\
 \sigma &\sim \text{gamma}(0.01, 0.01)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{17}$$

3. Results

3.1. Model validation

There was an increase in both the global accuracy and the F1 score going from v1.1 to v1.3 of the ICE CREAMS model (Fig. 1). Across the ~60,000 independently labelled validation pixels, v1.3 gained a global accuracy of 91 % and an F1 score of 0.7, while v1.1 achieved 88 % and

0.64 (a 3 and 5.5 % increase, respectively in global accuracy and F1). While v1.1 predicted 237 more true seagrass pixels than v1.3 (3.7 % more True Positives) it also incorrectly predicted 2097 more seagrass pixels (96 % more False Positives). This decrease in over-estimation of seagrass by v1.3 compared to v1.1 was the main reason for the newer models greater accuracy.

3.2. Largest seagrass hotspots in Europe

We found that across Europe there were 12 intertidal seagrass hotspots (Fig. 2), with the three greatest total hotspot areas ranging from the North to the South: North Frisian Wadden Sea at 14.6 km², Arcachon Bay at 6.06 km² and Ria Formosa at 5.64 km² (Fig. 2).

These seagrass hotspots range from the south of Europe (Ria Formosa: 37°N 7.9°W) up to the north (North Frisian Wadden Sea: 54.6°N 8.73°E), but there are clear differences in the distribution of cover within each hotspot, with southern sites showing dominance of highest cover classes (80–100 %), while northern sites show relatively lower cover (50–60 %) across the entirety of the hotspot (Fig. 3). This means that the cumulative intertidal seagrass area within these hotspots was smaller than the total hotspot area, with seagrass cumulatively covering 9.01 ± 0.865 km², 3.73 ± 0.362 km² and 2.09 ± 0.222 km² for North Frisian Wadden Sea, Arcachon Bay and Ria Formosa, respectively.

3.3. National patterns of intertidal seagrass area

When summarised at the country level, there were large variations in the total intertidal area available and the cumulative coverage by seagrass (Fig. 4). The country with the largest area of intertidal seagrass was Germany (67 ± 6.05 km²), followed by France (49 ± 4.15 km²). Yet, these countries also had the greatest total intertidal areas and associated uncertainty, meaning the proportion of their intertidal area covered by seagrass was relatively low (1.5 % and 2.7 % coverage, respectively). Other countries with smaller total intertidal areas, such as Spain and Portugal, showed greater proportional coverage (7.5 % and 5.6 % coverage, respectively) but smaller cumulative intertidal seagrass areas: 14 ± 1.48 km² and 17.7 ± 1.7 km², respectively. Across all countries, the average intertidal area covered by seagrass was 1.4 %, ranging from 7.5 % cover in Spain to 0.1 % cover in Belgium (Fig. 4).

Fig. 1. Validation results for both v1.1 and v1.3 of ICE CREAMS, showing Global accuracy and F1 Score. Colour denotes the proportion of the total pixels for a specific group and labels show how many pixels for a specific group.

Fig. 2. Intertidal seagrass hotspots across Europe. Radius and colour of circles, and colour and length of bars, show area of seagrass hotspots (km²).

3.4. Latitudinal shifts in seagrass cover

Across the Atlantic Coastline of Europe there was a clear increase in the proportion of the intertidal area covered by seagrass with decreasing latitude going from around 0 % at 58°N to around 5.4 % at 35°N (Fig. 5 a). However, the cover of seagrass that filled that area also showed clear latitudinal patterns (Fig. 5 b). Lower cover seagrass (e.g. 50–60 and 60–70 % cover) was more prevalent in higher latitudes and less prevalent in lower latitudes, going from ~19 % and ~17 % at 58°N to ~8.3 % and ~11 % at 35°N, while the highest cover (e.g. 80–90 and 90–100 % cover) showed the opposite trend, going from ~4.1 % and ~6.3 % at 58°N to ~11 % and ~32 % at 35°N. Medium cover seagrass classes (70–80 % cover) showed no clear trends, apart from an increase in mid latitudes.

3.5. Seasonal variation in 'peak' timing

When mapped at the European scale, there is a clear latitudinal gradient in the time of year when intertidal seagrass meadows on the European Atlantic and North Sea coasts are at their peak (Fig. 6). This pattern showed higher latitude (58°N) peaking in seagrass cover around

20th July (ranging from 30th June to 9th August), mid latitudes (46°N) around 8th September (ranging from 29th August to 18th September) and low latitudes (35°N) around 28th October (ranging from 8th October to 27th November), with an almost linear change along the whole latitudinal range.

4. Discussion

This work has summarised the first Europe-wide intertidal seagrass map using a harmonised methodology. Using open access data we found 12 seagrass hotspots, as well as clear almost linear patterns in seagrass cover and seagrass peak timing, with high cover of seagrass being more prevalent in low latitudes, low cover being more prevalent in high latitudes, and peak timing ranging from July–August in high latitudes to November–December in low latitudes.

Previous assessments of the main intertidal seagrass hotspots found here show some comparability in areas of seagrass cover (Cognat et al., 2018; Guimarães et al., 2012; Rigouin et al., 2022), while others indicate visual agreement in distribution patterns, albeit with model over-estimates for total cumulative area (Dolch et al., 2017; van Katwijk et al., 2024). This general consistency shows a high robustness of the

Fig. 3. The distribution of seagrass cover in North Frisian Wadden Sea: 54.6°N 8.73°E (a) and Ria Formosa: 37°N 7.9°W (b). Background images are grey-scale Sentinel-2 images from 2023 to 09-09 (a) and 2023-07-08 (b), while seagrass densities are derived from the maximum NDVI mosaics for each location.

current method to produce unbiased comparisons among European seagrasses, while also highlighting that, although some specific areas of intertidal seagrass were well documented, they were not measured in the same way. For example, the most recent documentation of Ria Formosa was carried out using one four band Planet satellite image from August 2019 and validated by field excursions performed from 2017 to 2020, producing an estimated total intertidal seagrass area of 10.33 km², regardless of the variability in seagrass percent cover (Ito et al., 2025). The other two of our largest hotspots are seagrass meadows that have undergone extensive changes over the last decades, either consistent decline over the last four decades in the case of Arcachon bay (Cognat et al., 2018; Rigouin et al., 2022) or declines followed by subsequent rapid recovery for the North Frisian Wadden Sea (Dolch et al., 2017; Dolch et al., 2013; van Katwijk et al., 2024). The inconsistency in methodologies across sites, and their variability over time, means caution should be taken before carrying out any direct comparisons.

Controlling for available intertidal area, we found a clear increase in seagrass occurrence towards southern Europe, alongside an increase in cover of the seagrass that was present. Studies have shown that terrestrial and marine diversity generally show patterns of decreased diversity with increased latitude (Kinlock et al., 2018; Nishizawa et al., 2022).

Fig. 4. European countries with their total intertidal area (not filled: km²) and total cumulative intertidal seagrass area (filled: km² ± 95 % error), while inset shows the total combined intertidal area (not filled: km²) and total cumulative intertidal seagrass area (filled: km² ± 95 % error). Note the scale follows a square root transformation.

While the current work does not assess associated diversity, habitat forming species, such as seagrasses, are highly associated with elevated biodiversity (Boyé et al., 2017; McCloskey and Unsworth, 2015). It is therefore likely that seagrass-associated biodiversity increases towards lower latitudes and that this pattern is reinforced by the concomitant increase in seagrass cover. Likewise, seagrass hotspots may also represent breakpoints in this latitudinal gradient, as they may also be hotspots of seagrass-associated faunal diversity, independent of latitude. While these general patterns hold across seagrasses, the individual species of seagrass will likely also drive patterns of species-associated fauna. Throughout Europe, there is a low level of intertidal seagrass diversity itself, with a maximum richness of three: *Zostera noltii*, *Zostera marina* and *Cymodocea nodosa*. The vast majority of detected seagrass here is expected to be *Zostera noltii* (Davies et al., 2024a), yet current methods are inadequate at consistently identifying vegetation to species levels. Therefore, it is likely the latitudinal increase in seagrass cover found here has implications for latitudinal patterns of seagrass species, as well as the associated biodiversity. However, this has not been consistently assessed on such spatial scales. Here, the clear increase in proportion of intertidal area covered by seagrass with decreasing latitude indicates that across the Atlantic and North Sea coastlines of Europe, the main drivers of seagrass cover are global scale processes. These drivers, or combinations of them, could include temperature (atmospheric and sea), illumination conditions (photoperiod, light intensity, Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR) etc.), nutrient and moisture availability (Gallinat et al., 2021; Piao et al., 2019). These environmental drivers are likely to also drive differences in intertidal seagrass species distributions (Short et al., 2007). As global weather patterns destabilise and extreme events increase in frequency, driven and exacerbated by human-induced climate change, it is clear that intertidal seagrasses will be heavily impacted and thus the biodiversity they harbour.

This latitudinal change in phenology has recently been described (Davies et al., 2024a), challenging previous assertions of minimally varying or consistent phenology in seagrass traits across Europe (Soissons et al., 2018a, 2018b). Here, the almost linear pattern with latitude implies that large-scale drivers (such as changes in temperature and PAR) are more influential than local drivers, like eutrophication, pollution, physical disturbance, topography, hydrology and tidal regimes. It is worth noting that the current estimates of ‘peak’ are in relation to the time when the highest NDVI was found. However, previous work has used the timing of the maximum cumulative extent of a site (Davies et al., 2024a), while other authors have assessed morphometric density based measures of phenology, such as leaf density, biomass or shoot density (Ondiviela et al., 2018; Short and Duarte,

Fig. 5. The change in percentage of intertidal area covered by seagrass across the latitudinal range of the Atlantic coastline of Europe (a) and the distribution of different seagrass cover ranges across the latitudinal range of Europe (b). Solid lines show model estimates, while shaded areas show 95 % confidence interval.

Fig. 6. Seasonality of intertidal seagrass 'peak' timing across latitude. Solid line shows model estimate, while shading shows 95 % confidence interval.

2001). While these methods of defining and estimating 'peak' intertidal seagrass create comparable results at the continental scale, care should be taken at the local scale, where management should utilise the estimate that best suits their objectives, whether they be seagrass restoration, seed harvesting, habitat protection or another service provided by the ecosystem.

4.1. Management implications

The European Nature Restoration Regulation is the first continent-wide law of its kind and sets binding targets to restore degraded ecosystems (EU, 2024), particularly those marine habitats such as seagrass beds or sediment bottoms that deliver significant benefits, including climate change mitigation. The law explicitly encourages the restoration of habitats with the most potential to capture and store carbon, and to prevent and reduce the impact of natural disasters. Our work is particularly pertinent in that context as this law establishes legally binding targets for the recovery of degraded ecosystems informed by harmonised, continent-wide baseline data. The facilitation of continent-wide restoration of degraded seagrass beds will require transboundary cooperation, and it is essential that nature managers have access to the best available temporarily and spatially explicit maps in order to help guide sustainable collection of donor material (e.g. seagrass seeds, shoots or sods) and to optimise site selection (e.g. identify areas of seagrass loss or sites with high restoration success likelihood). Without long-term datasets, it can be difficult to disentangle natural variation from anthropogenically driven trends, or to evidence the impact of any management intervention with certainty (Griffiths et al., 2020). Remote sensing coupled with in situ ground-truth data has the potential to

provide these long-term datasets, yet these data are, to date, either inconsistent or not available.

4.2. Consistency and coordination of data

It is recognised that across Europe, national seagrass maps are generally incomplete, and in nations where mapping data does exist, the methods used to collect the data are not always comparable across other European Member States. From 42 monitoring programmes in Europe, 51 different metrics were used to indicate environmental status (Marbà et al., 2013). This lack of consistency and coordination limits the utility of the data. It is also recognised that given the extent of Europe's intertidal flats, it is unfeasible to ground-truth all seagrass beds. Whilst citizen science efforts (e.g. [SeagrassSpotter.org](https://seagrassspotter.org)) are starting to aid filling this data gap, existing public and privately held data on seagrass distribution require collation, in order to validate and develop existing models. For example, the most recently published estimate of intertidal seagrass extent for Germany was $\sim 220 \text{ km}^2$ between 2011 and 2015 (Dolch et al., 2017). This is similar to our model estimate, yet the German estimates include all seagrasses above 5 % cover. Furthermore, there is around 10 years difference between these estimates, and German seagrass has seen rapid increases over previous decades, starting at less than 30 km^2 in 1994 and increasing by $\sim 730 \%$ over the following 20 years. Regardless, our estimate of $67 \pm 6.05 \text{ km}^2$ appears to be an underestimate, likely as we only consider seagrass covers above 50 %. Likewise, existing data from the Netherlands (van den Oever et al., 2023) suggests a mapped seagrass area of 4.58 km^2 in the South Wadden Sea suggesting our model provides an overestimation ($21.4 \pm 1.72 \text{ km}^2$). These discrepancies in estimates may be driven by differences in study method, but also perhaps due to reporting style. Here, the cumulative seagrass extent takes into consideration the cover throughout the extent (i.e. 2 pixels at 50 % = 100 m^2), while other estimates take the area of the full extent (i.e. 2 pixels at 50 % = 200 m^2). Alternatively, from our validation the classification has a false positive rate of around 4 %, which may lead to certain non-seagrass areas being predicted as such (Essex in the UK, *Personal Communication* Richard Unsworth). Without coordination between projects, methods may be difficult to compare or data may not be shared, making it hard to assess project outcomes or extract broader trends (Marbà et al., 2013). To address this observation challenge, there is a clear opportunity for European Member States to harmonise seagrass metrics using satellite remote sensing (Zoffoli et al., 2021). The open access product and interactive web map presented here represents an opportunity, both as a initial Europe-wide intertidal seagrass map, but also as a 'Call-to-Action' to data managers and the remote sensing community to accelerate the development of this product through joint cooperation. These data rely on the accuracy of a few other products (i.e. intertidal mask, atmospheric correction, ICE CREAMS classification and cover estimation from remote sensing); therefore improvements of these products would benefit the overall accuracy of this intertidal seagrass map. To achieve this, there is a clear and pressing need for data to be made available following FAIR principles (Miloslavich et al., 2018; Nordlund et al., 2024; Ratnarajah et al., 2022).

5. Conclusions

Our study provides an initial, up-to-date map of intertidal seagrass at the European scale, providing spatially, temporally and uncertainty explicit data at 10 m resolution. Firstly, we provided clear improvements to the ICE CREAMS classification, used this updated model to create a contemporary map of intertidal seagrass across Europe, by applying a robust and scalable methodology for continental scale intertidal seagrass mapping. This contemporary map and the accompanying data are provided as freely open-access in both the raw form and as a user-friendly tool for stakeholders and policy-makers. As with all continental scale maps, further validation and post-processing of data should be carried

out before use at local scales. Likewise, while we did show marked improvements in the ICE CREAMS classification, uncertainties persist in the methodology to mask and create composite imagery of the intertidal area, as well as in the classification itself. Thus, we lead a "Call-to-Action" for the availability of data following Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) principles to decrease these uncertainties. Nevertheless, this map provides critical and Europe-wide harmonised data that could be highly useful to regional, national and international management organisations. This will allow efforts to be made to protect, avoid further degradation and even aid restoration of this important marine ecosystem found at the interface between terrestrial and marine environments.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Bede Ffinian Rowe Davies: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Simon Oiry:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Mar Roca:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology. **Philippe Rosa:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation. **Maria Laura Zoffoli:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Dimitris Poursanidis:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Tobias Dolch:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Bárbara Ondiviela:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Cristina Galván:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Ana C. Brito:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Richard J. Lilley:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Laura L. Govers:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Martin Gade:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Laurent Barillé:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Pierre Gernez:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This work was a continuation from previous work to create the Intertidal Classification of Europe: Categorising Reflectance of Emerged Areas of Marine vegetation with Sentinel-2 (ICE CREAMS v1.0), which was supported through the BiCOME (Biodiversity of the Coastal Ocean: Monitoring with Earth Observation) project funded by the European Space Agency under 'Earth Observation Science for Society' element of FutureEO-1 BIODIVERSITY+PRECURSORS call, contract No. 4000135756/21/I-EF. This work was also supported through the REWRITE (Rewilding European Shorelines and Beyond) project funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement 101081357. This work was also supported by MarshA (TED2021-129973B-I00) project, funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by the European Union NextGenerationEU/PRTR.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2025.115116>.

Data availability

All data will be made open-access in an appropriate repository on acceptance of the publication.

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